

FUTURE COMMUNICATIONS PROGRAMME – ROAD TO 6G

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Future Comms R&D Programme (FCP) Overview

KEY POINTS

FUTURE TECH ASIA

Singapore is launching a \$50 million program to advance research on AI and cybersecurity

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- Singapore plans to invest around \$50 million in a program to support advanced communications and connectivity research, Deputy Prime Minister Heng Swee Keat announced.
- As part of the Future Communications Research & Development Programme, Singapore plans to set up new communications testbeds in 5G and beyond-5G.
- Singapore will also be launching the Singapore Trade Data Exchange, or SGTraDex, that will allow multiple stakeholders along the supply chain to share information such as real-time cargo locations.

- Prof. Tony Quek is the Director of FCP and FCP is hosted at SUTD
- FCP is from May 2021 – Jul 2025
- FCP will focus on 5G translation, 5G evolution, and 6G research
- Build up Singapore's communications and connectivity capabilities
- Strengthen international partnership
- Connectivity Testbed will focus on Open RAN 5G and beyond network
- Allows translation of 5G evolution and 6G research capabilities

FCCLab at SUTD

Mission:

- To accelerate cutting-edge research of 5G / 6G communications technologies
- To build Singapore's capability in this space
- Developing talent

Potential impacts:

- **For business:** to streamline *highly complex tasks of a networked system* in manufacturing, transportation, and other industrial sectors
- **For consumers:** to provide remote healthcare / education / entertainment experience *as smooth & personalized as the best in-person experience today*
- **For society:** to make the underlying communications & connectivity infrastructure *secure, reliable, and trustworthy*

FCCLab Testbed: Key features

Open: follow 3GPP & O-RAN standards to support easy plug-in & evaluation of research outcomes

Modular: components from multiple vendors can be easily integrated & individually upgraded

Software-defined: deployable in virtualized environment & leverage AI for intelligent orchestration

Reconfigurable: customizable for diverse use cases & adapt to changing environment / user needs

Research outcomes for individual components (e.g., CU, DU, or RIC) can be plugged into the testbed for validation

Industry collaborators can bring in their technologies for integration & testing in the testbed

Phase I of FCCLab (2021-2023): 5G Open RAN Network

Logical View

- Per 5GC support up to 128* BBU
- 10,000 simultaneous attached UE

- Per outdoor RRU support coverage distance
 - Pole-mounted: 180m
- Per Indoor RRU support coverage distance
 - Wall-mounted: 90m*
 - Ceiling-mounted: 60m*

Future Max
Expansion

5GC	x1
BBU	x128
FHGW	x128
RRU	x512

Key info:

- 50MHz 3.4-3.45GHz
- 400MHz 25.9-26.3GHz
- Downlink: 400Mbps+, uplink: 150Mbps+
- 3GPP Release 15, ORAN function split 7-2
- IEEE 1588v2 synchronization
- Tested using CPE (gemteks) and Samsung S21 Ultra phone

Open RAN

Brief Comparison between RAN and O-RAN

Open, Intelligent, and Cloud-Native

Traditional Radio Access Network (RAN)

- Vendor specific interface between Radio Unit, Baseband Unit, and Management system

Open RAN (O-RAN)

- Horizontal and vertical RAN disaggregation
- To avoid vendor lock-in & increase network agility and programmability

*Source : Omdia

Open RAN Market

The global C2 industry is increasingly recognising the importance of flexibility, cost-effectiveness, and resilience of O-RAN and given the current state of the O-RAN market, there is potential for growth. Key drivers of O-RAN market growth include flexibility, reduced cost, and supply chain diversity. The understatement of O-RAN's potential is under pronounced and there is opportunity for Singapore to build its strength here.

Open RAN Ecosystem

Proven Open and Interoperable Open RAN ecosystem

Open RAN Research

Potential research areas:

- Security and Trust in Open RAN
- AI/ML for Open RAN
- Sustainability in Open RAN
- Architecture towards 6G Open RAN
- Advanced RIC and real-time RIC (< 1ms)
- Spectrum management in Open RAN
- Flexible and programmable slicing for Open RAN
- Open RAN evolution for future NTN
- Open RAN evolution for future functionalities
- Massive antenna systems for Open RAN

Next Generation URLLC & IoT

Enhanced Massive IoT/URLLC

- URLLC looking beyond low-rate applications to 1-10Mbps applications with strict latency and reliability
- Enable operation in unlicensed band via dynamic channel access
- Sidelink transmission (D2D) allows direct coordination/communication among robots/controllers/cars

5G Drone Arena

- Drone Arena for research, education and outreach
- Private 5G network coverage
- Drone applications with 5G connectivity
- XR drone racing competition
- 3D Network Design
 - Expand with more technologies like edge computing, edge cameras, sensors, mmWave radio units
 - Human-AI-Machine interactions
 - Network of networks

Key Challenges

- Massive IoT with higher data rates
 - Coverage, delay, energy, cost, reliability, scalability
 - AI/ML for predictive control and scheduling
- Massive URLLC
 - Trade-off between latency and reliability for a scalable solution
 - AI/ML for predictive control and scheduling
- IoT over Non-Terrestrial Networks
 - Relook at random access schemes
 - Relook at PHY design
- Convergence of communications, computing, control, sensing, localization, and caching
 - Multitasking given a set of resources (“resource reuse”)
- Security, Privacy and Trustworthiness
 - Blockchain and Federated learning

Network as Sensors

Internet of Senses

- Usage of radio signals to sense the environment
 - Sub 6 GHz, mmWave, TeraHz
 - Pathloss measurements, reflections
- RF Sensing
 - Future UE will have many powerful sensors
 - Radar capability on a UE
- Reconfigurable intelligent surfaces
 - Control the wireless medium directly
 - Network intelligence and control will be key
- Sensing and control integration
 - Noisy and massive feedbacks
 - Automation through AI but too much data to train and label

Cyber-Physical Campus

Digital Scent Technology

More than 70% of our daily memories and emotions are triggered by smell.

Scent memory lasts 70% longer than auditory or visual memories.

Source: OVR Technology

- Two cohort classrooms with private 5G coverage
- Demonstrate concept of cyber-physical campus with learning as a use case
- Can be used to demonstrate concept of internet of senses
- Virtual Campus/Office:
 - 3D vs 2D in remote work/learning environment
 - New way of communication

Key Challenges

- Latency requirements
 - End-to-end delay lower than 1ms
- Extreme high bandwidth requirements
 - Truly immersive experience with holographic communications
- eMBB + URLLC + ambient intelligence
 - This is what makes 6G distinctly different from 5G
- New fundamental theory in communications
 - Shannon capacity no longer serves as a design guideline
- AI/ML
 - Personalized experiences
- Killer applications
 - Smart healthcare, smart education, smart home, smart travel

Metaverse

Metaverse

- **What is Metaverse?**
 - The metaverse is the next generation of the mobile internet; the metaverse will help you connect with people you aren't physically in the same place

Connect

Play

Work

Shop

Connectivity for Metaverse

- VR/AR/MR/XR
- mmWave Radar
- 5G + Edge Computing
- Metaverse
- Integrates our senses with cyber and physical worlds through 5G
- Web3: Enabler for new customer experience
 - 3D Native Digital Experience
 - Sense of Presence
 - Token Economy
 - Remote Collaboration
 - Social Interaction
 - NFT Membership

Key Challenges

- Metaverse needs 6G!
- Latency requirements
 - End-to-end delay lower than 1ms
- Extreme high bandwidth requirements
 - Truly immersive experience with XR experience
- eMBB + URLLC + ambient intelligence
 - This is what makes 6G distinctly different from 5G
- Cm-level positioning accuracy
- AI Controller for physical and cyber space integration
 - Personalized experiences
- Integration of blockchain, IoT, HCI, VR, MEC, Cloud, and more

Trust & Security

O-RAN Security

- Asia & Pacific OTIC in Singapore
- O-RAN Security will be the focus / key differentiating point for this OTIC
- This OTIC serves as a platform to work with local/overseas vendors and partners

NEWS RELEASE 28-FEB-2023

SUTD to launch south-east Asia's first O-RAN Open Testing and Integration Centre (OTIC)

Business Announcement

SINGAPORE UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY AND DESIGN

SUTD to Launch South-east Asia's First O-RAN Open Testing and Integration Centre (OTIC)

Announced at the Mobile World Congress Barcelona (MWC) 2023, Singapore University of Technology and Design (SUTD) will launch a new O-RAN[1] Asia & Pacific Open Testing and Integration Centre (OTIC) in Singapore. As part of Singapore's S\$70 million Future Communications R&D Programme (FCP) supported by Singapore's Infocomm Media Development Authority (IMDA) and the National Research Foundation, Singapore (NRF), the Asia & Pacific OTIC in Singapore will be co-located within SUTD's Future Communications Connectivity (FCC) lab.

Quantum Safe Network

- National Quantum-Safe Network (NQSN) aims to establish a nationwide platform and a field-deployed testbed for a systematic construction of quantum-safe communication technologies
- Explore use of quantum key distribution (QKD) to secure future communications applications
- Fiber link from FCC Lab to QCT at NUS is around 47km, with lowest loss around 13.5 dB at 1550nm.
- Plan to evaluate sending a quantum source and performance of QKD

Key Challenges

- AI/ML Security
- Strong isolation, attestation, runtime monitoring
- Trust management for different service scenarios across multiple domains/ stakeholders and through the lifecycle
- Attacks that exploit cloud and MEC vulnerabilities/weakness
- Attacks via open interfaces/ disaggregated components/open-source software/open API
- Attacks to service scenarios/use cases from different verticals

Phase II of FCCLab (2023-2025):

Plan:

- Opening of Asia & Pacific OTIC in SG (Q3 2023) with expansion plans
- Deployment of multi-vendor O-RAN networks
- Coordination of mmWave and 3.5Hz 5G networks
- Digital twins
- 5G/6G NTN testbed (hardware + simulator)
- Trial of new technologies like RIS, hologram
- Remote connected testbeds

Thank you!